

**IMPACT OF VITAMIN D ON PHYSICAL EFFICIENCY AND EXERCISE PERFORMANCE—A
REVIEW****Shkiryak A.***CEO and chief medical officer “Shkiryak Clinic”**Ukraine**Neurosurgeon**MD, MsSc**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2282-8285>***Khanenko S.***“Shkiryak Clinic”**Ukraine**Family doctor**MD, MBA**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-4237-1158>***Abstract**

Vitamin D deficiency amongst athletes and the general population seems to be a prominent problem. The most recognized role of vitamin D is its regulation of calcium homeostasis; there is a strong relationship between vitamin D and bone health. Moreover, its concentrations are associated with muscle function and immune response in both the general and athletic populations. Vitamin D level is strongly connected with the presence of VDRs (vitamin D receptors) in most human extracellular cells. Expression of multiple myogenic transcription factors enhancing muscle cell proliferation and differentiation is caused by an exposure of skeletal muscles to vitamin D. The aim of this review is to summarize current understanding of the significance of vitamin D on exercise performance and physical efficiency, as well to analyze the impact of vitamin D on multiple potential mechanisms. More high-quality research studies, considering free 25(OH)D as a better marker of vitamin D status, the baseline level of 25(OH)D and multiple pathways of vitamin D acting and usage in athletes are required.

Keywords: 25(OH)D, VDR, VDBP, athlete, physical efficiency, exercise performance, vitamin D deficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Vitamin D is a group of steroid compounds demonstrating the same biological activity, mainly associated with affecting calcium phosphate economy. It occurs in nature in the forms of vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol) and vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol). Vitamin D₂ is produced by fungi and yeast by UVB-exposure of ergosterol (provitamin D₂), therefore, ergocalciferol is found in sun-dried mushroom products and in plant-based products (as a result of contamination with fungi) (1, 2). Accordingly, vitamin D₂ is generally known as a plant form of vitamin D, whereas vitamin D₃ is produced by UVB-exposure of 7-dehydrocholesterol (provitamin D₃) in the skin of many vertebrate animals, including humans. Cholecalciferol can be provided by consuming animal products like fatty fish (mackerel, salmon, sardines), fish oil, eggs and liver or, in smaller amounts, meat, dairy products, offal and poultry (3). Nevertheless, over 90% of vitamin D in the human body is formed in the skin tissue influenced by sunlight. Provitamin D (7-dehydrocholesterol) is converted under ultraviolet B (UVB) rays to provitamin D₃ and ultimately to vitamin D₃ (4). It is certain that 25(OH)D can be increased by vitamin D supplementation, proper nutrition and exposing uncovered skin to sun radiation (sun angle should be over 30°) (6). There are many other factors that decrease the level of vitamin D, such as obesity (adiposity may decrease bioavailability of 25-hydroxyvitamin D) (7), liver failure, senectitude, darker skin tone or sunscreen use (8,9,10). Smoking cigarettes also has a significant negative influence on the level of vitamin D (11). Beyond modifiable factors

there are dimensions such as genetic determinants, individual variations (12) or age that are not modifiable (13). The relationship between gender and vitamin D deficiency or 25(OH)D level is inconsistent and elaborate in non-athletes. Verdoia et al. observed significantly lower 25(OH)D levels in females (female 14.5 ± 10.9 ng/mL vs. male 15.9 ± 9.5 ng/mL, $p = 0.007$), which might be strongly related to the older age of women participating in the study comparing to men ($p < 0.001$). Moreover, a higher rate of vitamin D deficiency occurred especially in post-menopausal women. (14). On the contrary, the study of AlQuainz et al. identified a higher prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among males when compared to females (72.0% ($n = 695$) vs. 64.0% ($n = 1191$)) (15). Likewise, the study of Johnson et al., conducted on morbidly obese patients, showed that male patients had significantly lower mean 25(OH)D concentrations than female patients (50.0 ± 22.0 nmol/L versus 53.6 ± 22.4 nmol/L ($p = 0.001$)) and a higher rate of vitamin D deficiency than women (56% vs. 47%; $p < 0.001$) (16). Gender differences can be related with both known (for example, more men smoke cigarettes and are less likely than women to avoid high-fat foods, women wear hijabs covering the whole body) and unknown habits. The differences by sex may be due to variations in body fat percentage and body size (17). The decrease in vitamin D bioavailability is thought to be due to sequestration of vitamin D in adipose tissue after cutaneous synthesis or dietary intake, although the exact mechanism is not yet known. However, the study of Halliday et al. showed no difference in vitamin D status depending on sex in athletes ($p = 0.10$). Any cor-

relations between body mass, BMI or body fat percentage adjusted by sex were also not found in athletes. The reason for a lack of a significant correlation between vitamin D status and adiposity in this study is most likely explained by the reduced body fat range of the athlete population. Moreover, different sport disciplines were studied in relation to male and female athletes (18).

Vitamin D insufficiency seems to be a very prominent problem amongst athletes and the general population (19, 20). The evidence available suggests that there is a cause for concern regarding the vitamin D concentration of athletes depending on sun exposure. The results of a huge meta-analysis of 23 studies with 2313 athletes demonstrated that 56% of them had vitamin D inadequacy. Vitamin D insufficiency significantly varied by latitude, also, it was higher during winter and at the beginning of the spring season (21) and for those athletes doing indoor sport activities (22). The difference between outdoor and indoor athletes is noticeable in the study of Aydin et al., which showed the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in 59% of outdoor athletes and 64% of indoor athletes. The study was conducted during winter season [4]. Peeling et al. found significantly lower vitamin D status in indoor (90 ± 28 nmol/L) compared to outdoor (131 ± 35 nmol/L) athletes ($p = 0.0001$). Considering the predominant training environment during the summer season, 50% trained predominately indoors (31 gymnastics, 5 diving) and 30.6% trained predominately outdoors (10 sailing, 7 field hockey, 3 athletics, 2 rowing) (23). Halliday et al. documented that 25(OH)D concentrations changed across time ($p = 0.001$) and averaged 49.0 ± 16.6 , 30.5 ± 9.4 , and 41.9 ± 14.6 ng/mL in the fall, winter, and spring, respectively, in a group of 41 collegiate athletes (12 indoor (wrestling, swimming, basketball) and 29 outdoor athletes (football, soccer, cross-country or track and field, and cheerleading/dance)). Vitamin D levels were significantly higher in outdoor compared with indoor athletes in the fall (53.1 ± 17.4 vs. 39.3 ± 8.9 ng/mL, $p = 0.013$); in the winter or spring, vitamin D concentrations were higher in outdoor athletes, but these differences were not statistically significant. Of the athletes studied, 75.6% in the fall, 15.2% in the winter, and 36.0% in the spring had optimal 25(OH)D status (40 ng/mL was the cut-off for optimal status). Neither total vitamin D intake nor intake from food alone differed across time or with sex or training location ($p < 0.05$) (18).

METABOLISM OF VITAMIN D AND MECHANISMS OF VITAMIN D RECEPTOR

The activity of vitamin D is highly connected with cytochrome P450 enzymes which are responsible for both activation (25-hydroxylase, 1α -hydroxylase) and deactivation (24-hydroxylase) of vitamin D. Firstly, 25(OH)D is produced in the liver, from D2 or D3 with the contribution of CYP2R1 (25-hydroxylase), and then in the kidneys, the biologically active form of vitamin D—1,25(OH)₂D—is synthesized by CYP27B1 (1α -hydroxylase) from 25(OH)D. Inactivation of vitamin D goes gradually by 24-hydroxylase that forms inactive metabolites 24,25-dihydroxyvitamin D and 1,24,25-trihydroxyvitamin D from 25(OH)D and

1,25(OH)₂D, respectively. In the end, CYP3A4 degrades them (24). The enzymes mentioned above are magnesium-dependent; optimal magnesium concentration, depending on baseline level of 25(OH)D, can be helpful to reaching proper 25(OH)D target concentration (25).

The biological function of vitamin D, in principle 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D—the active metabolite—is unspecifically mediated by binding to a single vitamin D receptor (VDR) that is expressed in several tissues (26,27). Moreover, direct influence of 1,25(OH)₂D is also possible through specific plasma membrane receptors (28).

A VDR consists of three main domains: the C-domain that binds DNA, the E-domain that connects with a ligand and the activating F-domain. The vitamin D receptor is closely connected to RXR (retinoic acid receptor); the 5' arm of the nucleotide sequence of VDRE acts with RXR, and for VDR, it is the 3' arm. As it is a ligand-dependent transcription factor, it binds VDR and RXR along with some other proteins and activators (SARC1-3 and DRIP205), creating a transcription complex at the VDREs so the phosphorylation is initiated (29).

It seems to be significant to mention the vitamin D-binding protein (VDBP) which is produced by hepatic parenchymal cells' glycoprotein; its main function is linking almost 90% of 25(OH)D and 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ circulating in serum. Out of the total 25(OH)D, albumin binds approximately 10% and less than 1% remains free (albumin-bound and "free" are the only bioavailable forms). Black men have lower levels of VDBP than white men, having lower mean concentration of total serum 25(OH)D at the same time (Black 25.0 ± 14.7 vs. White 37.4 ± 14.0 ; $p < 0.001$) (30,31).

VITAMIN D IN SPORT PERFORMANCE

Due to vitamin D insufficiency in the population, many studies undertake the topic of correlation between vitamin D insufficiency and impaired sport performance, defined as skeletal muscle function. Vitamin D is one of the most regularly used dietary supplements amongst athletes worldwide and is the number one supplement taken by athletes with a physical impairment (32, 33). Close et al. found a significantly positive correlation between vitamin D₃ supplementation (5000 IU per day for 8-weeks) and the improvement of musculoskeletal performance, especially in vertical jump height and 10-m sprint times. The study was a placebo-controlled trial conducted on 61 male athletes coming from different sports (soccer, rugby, flat and hunt jockeys) and 30 controls who were apparently healthy non-athletic individuals. It was found that 62% of the athletes had a baseline level of total serum 25(OH)D below 50 nmol/L and also that 73% of the controls were 25(OH)D-deficient or had inadequate 25(OH)D level. Total serum 25(OH)D significantly increased from baseline in the vitamin D treated group of athletes (34).

Moreover, Książek et al. showed that there is a positive correlation between vitamin D levels and sport performance. They enrolled 25 representatives of the Polish National judo team who were in the general preparation period and were performing almost the same exercises. It was found that 80% of the athletes

were vitamin D deficient, with less than 30 ng/mL 25(OH)D in the baseline. The results of the study presented a statistically positive correlation between 25(OH)D concentration and the power of vertical jump. There was also significant correlation with left hand grip strength and total work for both the right and left lower extremities during extension (35).

Rowing is a discipline where most of the energy is supplied via aerobic metabolism similar to other endurance types of sports. There is a correlation between aerobic power and high maximum oxygen consumption (VO_{2max}) where the transport of oxygen plays a key role. It is coherent that improving hematological levels is a way to enhance rowers' athletic performance. Thirty-six elite male rowers were randomly separated into a control group (CG, $n = 18$, height 181.05 ± 3.39 cm, body mass 77.02 ± 7.55 kg) and a group supplemented with 3000 IU of vitamin D/day for eight weeks (VD3G, $n = 18$, height: 179.70 ± 9.07 , body mass: 76.19 ± 10.07 kg). Mielgo-Ayuso et al. intended to check if vitamin D supplementation was a suitable factor appealing to hematological and iron metabolism profile. All of the athletes had baseline suboptimal 25(OH)D concentrations (26.24 ± 8.18 ng/mL) and the tests were carried out in the spring months (April–June) in Spain. Statistically, a significant increase in the serum concentration of 25(OH)D in the VD3G after 8 weeks (T2) was observed (T1 26.24 ± 8.18 ng/mL vs. T2 48.12 ± 10.88 ng/mL; $p < 0.001$). In the CG (control group) no statistically significant changes were noticed (T1 30.76 ± 6.95 ng/mL vs. T2 35.14 ± 7.96 ng/mL; $p = 0.056$). Significant differences in the group-by-time interaction of hemoglobin ($p = 0.009$), hematocrit ($p = 0.019$) and transferrin ($p = 0.007$) between the two groups through the study were observed. Moreover, in the CG, a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in hemoglobin during the study (T1 15.54 ± 0.88 ng/mL vs. T2 15.09 ± 0.82 ng/mL), and a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in VD3G in transferrin levels over 8 weeks (T1: 254.22 ± 20.69 vs. 270.44 ± 20.08 mg/dL) were observed. Although, in both groups, all body composition measures (body mass, BMI, sum 4 skinfolds, fat mass and free fat mass) presented significant differences during the study ($p < 0.05$), the group-by-time interaction of them between groups did not show any significant difference ($p > 0.05$). All rowers followed the same training program (the average weekly hours of training were 15 during the study). These results show that vitamin D supplementation affects hematological parameters and can enhance aerobic power by increasing VO_{2max} . However, authors did not give any information as to if the rowers were at the beginning or in the middle of their training season, which would have a relevant impact on the interpretation of results. Moreover, the study group of 36 rowers divided into two groups seems to be too small and limiting (36).

Analysis of the results of Koundourakis et al.'s research on 67 Caucasian male professional soccer players of three Greek football teams showed some interesting findings that not only exposure to UVB but also reduction of training stress may have a good influence on serum vitamin D levels. Vitamin D concentration was found to be increased significantly following the six-

week off-season period (47.24 ± 13.50 ng/mL) compared to baseline (34.41 ± 7.08 ng/mL) while at the same time, all measured performance parameters decreased. Moreover, the study demonstrated a significant positive linear association between 25(OH)D level and muscle strength as evaluated by squat and counter-movement jumps, sprinting ability (10- and 20-m) and aerobic capacity— VO_{2max} —in professional soccer players. According to this study, vitamin D levels probably play a significant supportive role in sport performance (37).

The study of Jastrzębska et al. was conducted on 36 soccer players (age: 17.5 ± 0.6 years, body mass 71.3 ± 6.9 kg, BMI 22.2 ± 1.8 kg/m²) who were members of a sports school (Poland) that educated the highly talented youth. Players were divided into two groups: the placebo one, $n = 16$ and the experimental one, $n = 20$ (which was vitamin D3 supplemented). The selection was done deliberately into homogenous groups and even the number of players of the same field position was equal. Initial 25(OH)D levels did not differ between supplemented and placebo groups (48.5 ± 8.6 vs. 47.5 ± 16.2 mmol/L, $p = 0.817$). In the supplemented group, the plasma 25(OH)D level increased significantly after the intervention (initial 48.5 ± 8.6 mmol/L, after intervention 106.3 ± 26.6 mmol/L, $p < 0.0001$), while in the placebo group, only non-significant changes were observed (initial 47.5 ± 16.2 mmol/L, after intervention 43.5 ± 16.7 mmol/L, $p = 0.228$). The following variables improved significantly compared to the placebo group: maximal running velocity (V_{max} , $p = 0.017$), running velocity at lactate threshold (V_{LT} , $p < 0.0001$), V_{LT}/V_{max} ($p = 0.000006$), maximal heart rate ($p = 0.0001$), physical work capacity ($p < 0.0001$) and maximal oxygen uptake ($p < 0.0001$) (38).

In the above studies, the subjects were supplemented with daily doses of vitamin D. Wyon et al. separated 22 judo athletes into two groups and supplemented one with a one-time dose of 150,000 IU. Nevertheless, the treatment group demonstrated a significant increase in muscle strength between days 1 and 8 ($p = 0.01$) (39).

On the other hand, a number of published reports fail to document any statistically significant impact of increasing vitamin D level on exercise performance (30). A recent placebo-controlled double-blind study conducted on 36 top Polish young junior soccer players, aged 17.5 ± 0.6 years, did not demonstrate statistically significant difference between the placebo and the supplemented with vitamin D groups. After eight weeks of the same high-intensity soccer training activity, it was found that there was just a little positive difference in physical activity indicators (time–motion parameters and heart rate) in comparison to placebo group. Baseline level of 25-hydroxyvitamin D did not differ significantly between supplemented (48.5 ± 8.6 nmol/L) and non-supplemented groups (47.5 ± 16.2 nmol/L) (40).

Furthermore, Orysiak et al. conducted a cross-sectional study on a group of 50 adolescent male ice hockey players. They found that vitamin D insufficiency is highly prevalent in this group, nevertheless, there was no positive correlation between serum 25(OH)D concentration and isometric muscle strength,

vertical jump performance, or repeated sprint ability (RSA) after adjusting for age, training experience, fat mass, fat free mass and height. Exercise performance was evaluated using isometric strength measures of upper and lower extremities, vertical jump performance and RSA (41).

A study on 22 rugby players supplemented with 50 000 IU of cholecalciferol (equivalent to 3570 IU/day) or placebo once every two weeks over 11–12 weeks demonstrated significant increase of serum 25(OH)D concentrations in the treatment group compared to placebo ($p < 0.001$). Performance in five of the six tests, including the primary outcome variable of 30-m sprint time, did not differ between the vitamin D supplemented and placebo groups ($p > 0.05$). Only performance on the weighted reverse-grip chin up was significantly higher in players receiving vitamin D compared with placebo ($p = 0.002$) (42).

Todd et al. observed similar findings in a research on 43 Gaelic football players, who received twelve-week daily supplementation with 3000 IU of vitamin D during wintertime. The vitamin D supplementation had no significant effect on VO_2 max ($p = 0.375$), skeletal muscle and lung function, or vertical jump height when compared to the placebo group ($p = 0.797$). It also had no significant effect on left or right handgrip strength ($p = 0.146$ and $p = 0.266$, respectively). Although the concentration of 25(OH)D increased ($p = 0.006$), there was no correlation between total 25(OH)D and measures of physical performance ($p > 0.05$) (43).

SUMMARY

According to the review, it is undoubtedly important to conduct another high-quality research study. One of the main aspects that should be taken into account is important evidence suggestive that free (bioavailable) 25(OH)D can turn out to be a better marker of vitamin D status. Many researchers do not take under consideration that athletes may require an increased supply of vitamin D to fulfill muscle metabolism requirements because of potential pathways of vitamin D usage. Significant debate seems to be needed to determine and standardize a classification of vitamin D deficiency.

Summarizing the results of this review, there are many incompatible reports about correlation between vitamin D supplementation and exercise performance for athletes. It is still uncertain if vitamin D supplementation shall be definitely recommended, however it seems to give beneficial effects while incorporating the baseline level of vitamin D status in planning studies and analyzing the results.

References

- Jäpelt R.B., Jakobsen J. Vitamin D in plants: A review of occurrence, analysis, and biosynthesis. *Front. Plant Sci.* 2013;4:136. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2013.00136.
- Cardwell G., Bornman J.F., James A.P., Black L.J. A review of mushrooms as a potential source of dietary Vitamin, D. *Nutrients.* 2018;10:1498. doi: 10.3390/nu10101498.
- Holick M.F. Vitamin D: Importance in the prevention of cancers, type 1 diabetes, heart disease, and osteoporosis. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 2004;79:362–371. doi: 10.1093/ajcn/79.3.362.
- Aydın C.G., Dinçel Y.M., Arıkan Y., Taş S.K., Deniz S. The effects of indoor and outdoor sports participation and seasonal changes on vitamin D levels in athletes. *SAGE Open Med.* 2019;7:2050312119837480. doi: 10.1177/2050312119837480.
- Owens D.L., Sharples A.P., Polydorou I., Alwan N., Donovan T., Tang J., Fraser W.D., Cooper R.G., Morton J.P., Stewart C., et al. A systems-based investigation into vitamin D and skeletal muscle repair, regeneration, and hypertrophy. *Am. J. Physiol. Endocrinol. Metab.* 2015;309:E1019–E1031. doi: 10.1152/ajpendo.00375.2015.
- Cook R., Thomas V., Martin R. Can treating vitamin D deficiency reduce exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease? *BMJ.* 2019;364:11025. doi: 10.1136/bmj.11025.
- Manson J.E., Cook N.R., Lee I.M., Christen W., Bassuk S.S., Mora S., Gibson H., Gordon D., Copeland T., D'Agostino D., et al. Vitamin D supplements and prevention of cancer and cardiovascular disease. *New Engl. J. Med.* 2019;380:33–44. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1809944.
- Hamilton S.A., McNeil R., Hollis B.W., Davis D.L., Winkler J., Cook C., Warner G., Bivens B., McShane P., Wagner C.L. Profound vitamin d deficiency in a diverse group of women during pregnancy living in a sun-rich environment at latitude 32° N. *Hindawi Publ. Corp. Int. J. Endocrinol.* 2010;2010:917428. doi: 10.1155/2010/917428.
- Macdonald H.M. Contributions of sunlight and diet to Vitamin D status. *Calcif. Tissue Int.* 2013;92:163–176. doi: 10.1007/s00223-012-9634-1.
- Zürcher S.J., Quadri A., Huber A., Thomas L., Close G.L., Brunner S., Noack P., Gojanovic B., Kriemler S. Predictive factors for Vitamin D concentrations in Swiss Athletes: A cross-sectional study. *Sports Med. Int. Open.* 2018;2:E148–E156. doi: 10.1055/a-0669-0791.
- Piazzolla G., Castrovilli A., Liotino V., Vulpi M.R., Fanelli M., Mazzocca A., Candigliota M., Berardi E., Resta O., Sabbà C., et al. Metabolic syndrome and Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD): The interplay among smoking, insulin resistance and vitamin D. *PLoS ONE.* 2017;12:e0186708. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0186708.
- Grzešek G., Janiszewska E., Malinowski B., Kubica A., Wiciński M. Adherence in patients with atrial fibrillation treated with dabigatran. *Kardiol. Pol.* 2018;11:1562–1563. doi: 10.5603/KP.a2018.0194.
- Malinowski B., Zalewska K., Węsierska A., Sokolowska M.M., Socha M., Liczner G., Pawlak-Osińska K., Wiciński M. Intermittent Fasting in Cardiovascular Disorders—An Overview. *Nutrients.* 2019;11:673. doi: 10.3390/nu11030673.
- Verdoia M., Schaffer A., Barbieri L., Di Giovine G., Marino P., Suryapranata H., De Luca G. Impact of gender difference on vitamin D status and its relationship with the extent of coronary artery disease. *Nutr. Metab. Cardiovasc. Dis. Nmed.* 2015;25:464–470. doi: 10.1016/j.numecd.2015.01.009.
- AlQuaiz A.M., Kazi A., Fouda M., Alyousefi N. Age and gender differences in the prevalence and

correlates of vitamin D deficiency. *Arch. Osteoporos.* 2018;13:49. doi: 10.1007/s11657-018-0461-5.

16. Johnson L.K., Hofso D., Aasheim E.T., Tanbo T., Holven K.B., Andersen L.F., Røislien J., Hjeltnes J. Impact of gender on vitamin D deficiency in morbidly obese patients: A cross-sectional study. *Eur. J. Clin. Nutr.* 2012;66:83–90. doi: 10.1038/ejcn.2011.140.

17. Al-Horani H., Abu Dayyih W., Mallah E., Hamad M., Mima M., Awad R., Arafat T. Nationality, gender, age, and body mass index influences on Vitamin D concentration among elderly patients and young Iraqi and Jordanian in Jordan. *Biochem. Res. Int.* 2016;2016:8920503. doi: 10.1155/2016/8920503.

18. Halliday T.M., Peterson N.J., Thomas J.J., Kleppinger K., Hollis B.W., Larson-Meyer D.E. Vitamin D status relative to diet, lifestyle, injury, and illness in college athletes. *Med. Sci. Sports Exerc.* 2011;43:335–343. doi: 10.1249/MSS.0b013e3181eb9d4d.

19. Desbrow B., Burd N.A., Tarnopolsky M., Moore D.R., Elliott-Sale K.J. Nutrition for special populations: Young, female, and masters athletes. *Int. J. Sport Nutr. Exerc. Metab.* 2019;29:220–227. doi: 10.1123/ijnsnem.2018-0269.

20. Aspell N., Laird E., Healy M., Shannon T., Lawlor B., O'Sullivan M. The prevalence and determinants of Vitamin D status in community-dwelling older adults: Results from the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) Nutrients. 2019;11:1253. doi: 10.3390/nu11061253.

21. Kleine C.E., Obi Y., Streja E., Hsiung J.T., Park C., Holick M.F., Kalantar-Zadeh K. Seasonal variation of serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D and parameters of bone and mineral disorder in dialysis patients. *Bone.* 2019;124:158–165. doi: 10.1016/j.bone.2019.03.003.

22. Farrokhyar F., Tabasinejad R., Dao D., Peterson D., Ayeni O.R., Hadioonzadeh R., Bhandari M. Prevalence of Vitamin D inadequacy in Athletes: A systematic-review and meta-analysis. *Sports Med.* 2015;45:365–378. doi: 10.1007/s40279-014-0267-6.

23. Peeling P., Fulton S.K., Binnie M., Goodman C. Training environment and Vitamin D status in Athletes. *Int. J. Sports Med.* 2013;34:248–252. doi: 10.1055/s-0032-1321894.

24. Lee D.H., Kim J.H., Jung M.H., Cho M.C. Total 25-hydroxy vitamin D level in cerebrospinal fluid correlates with serum total, bioavailable, and free 25-hydroxy vitamin D levels in Korean population. *PLoS ONE.* 2019;14:e0213389. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0213389.

25. Dai Q., Zhu X., Manson J.E., Song Y., Li X., Franke A.A., Costello R.B., Rosanoff A., Nian H., Fan L., et al. Magnesium status and supplementation influence vitamin D status and metabolism: Results from a randomized trial. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 2018;108:1249–1258. doi: 10.1093/ajcn/nqy274.

26. Demay M.B. Mechanism of Vitamin D receptor action. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 2006;1068:204–213. doi: 10.1196/annals.1346.026.

27. Dattilo G., Casale M., Avventuroso E., Laganà P. Vitamin D dietary supplementation: Relationship with chronic heart failure. *J. AOAC Int.* 2018;101:939–941. doi: 10.5740/jaoacint.17-0447.

28. Dittfeld A., Gwizdek K., Koszowska A., Fizia K. Multidirectional effect of vitamin D. *Ann. Acad. Med. Silesiensis.* 2014;68:1.

29. DeLuca H.F. Overview of general physiologic features and functions of vitamin D. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 2004;80:1689S–1696S. doi: 10.1093/ajcn/80.6.1689S.

30. Owens D.J., Allison R., Close G.L. Vitamin D and the athlete: Current perspectives and new challenges. *Sports Med.* 2018;48(Suppl. 1):3–16. doi: 10.1007/s40279-017-0841-9.

31. Hannan M.T., Litman H.J., Araujo A.B., McLennan C.E., McLean R.R., McKinlay J.B., Chen T.C., Holick M.F. Serum 25-Hydroxyvitamin D and bone mineral density in a racially and ethnically diverse group of men. *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.* 2008;93:40–46. doi: 10.1210/jc.2007-1217.

32. Madden R.F., Shearer J., Legg D., Parnell J.A. Evaluation of dietary supplement use in wheelchair rugby athletes. *Nutrients.* 2018;10:1958. doi: 10.3390/nu10121958.

33. Owens D.J., Fraser W.D., Close G.L. Vitamin D and the athlete: Emerging insights. *Eur. J. Sport Sci.* 2015;15:73–84. doi: 10.1080/17461391.2014.944223.

34. Close G.L., Russell J., Copley J.N., Owens D.J., Wilson G., Gregson W., Fraser W.D., Morton J.P. Assessment of vitamin D concentration in nonsupplemented professional athletes and healthy adults during the winter months in the UK: Implications for skeletal muscle function. *J. Sports Sci.* 2013;31:344–353. doi: 10.1080/02640414.2012.733822.

35. Książek A., Dziubek W., Pietraszewska J., Słowińska-Lisowska M. Relationship between 25(OH)D levels and athletic performance in elite Polish judoists. *Biol. Sport.* 2018;35:191–196. doi: 10.5114/biolSport.2018.74195.

36. Mielgo-Ayuso J., Calleja-González J., Urdampilleta A., León-Guereño P., Córdova A., Caballero-García A., Fernandez-Lázaro D. Effects of Vitamin D supplementation on haematological values and muscle recovery in elite male traditional rowers. *Nutrients.* 2018;10:1968. doi: 10.3390/nu10121968.

37. Koundourakis N.E., Androulakis N.E., Malliaraki N., Margioris A.N. Vitamin D and exercise performance in professional soccer players. *PLoS ONE.* 2014;9:e101659. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0101659.

38. Jastrzębska M., Kaczmarczyk M., Michalczyk M., Radziński Ł., Stępień P., Jastrzębska J., Wakułuk D., Díaz Suárez A.D., López Sánchez G.F., Cięszczyk P., et al. Can supplementation of Vitamin D improve aerobic capacity in well trained youth soccer players? *J. Hum. Kinet.* 2018;61:63–72. doi: 10.2478/hukin-2018-0033.

39. Wyon M.A., Wolman R., Nevill A.M., Cloak R., Metsios G.S., Gould D., Ingham A., Koutedakis Y. Acute effects of Vitamin D3 supplementation on muscle strength in judo athletes: A randomized placebo-controlled, double-blind trial. *Clin. J. Sport Med. Off. J. Can. Acad. Sport Med.* 2016;26:279–284. doi: 10.1097/JSM.0000000000000264.

40. Skalska M., Nikolaidis P.T., Knechtle B., Rosemann T.J., Radziński Ł., Jastrzębska J., Kaczmarczyk M., Myśliwiec A., Dragos P., López-Sánchez G.F., et al. Vitamin D supplementation and physical activity of young soccer players during high-intensity

training. *Nutrients*. 2019;11:349. doi: 10.3390/nu11020349.

41. Orysiak J., Mazur-Rozycka J., Fitzgerald J., Starczewski M., Malczewska-Lenczowska J., Busko K. Vitamin D status and its relation to exercise performance and iron status in young ice hockey players. *PLoS ONE*. 2018;13:e0195284. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0195284.

42. Fairbairn K.A., Ceelen I.J.M., Skeaff C.M., Cameron C.M., Perry T.L. Vitamin D3 supplementation does not improve sprint performance in professional rugby players: A randomised, placebo-controlled

double blind intervention study. *Int. J. Sport Nutr. Exerc. Metab.* 2018;28:1–9. doi: 10.1123/ijnsnem.2017-0157.

43. Todd J.J., McSorley E.M., Pourshahidi L.K., Madigan S.M., Laird E., Healy M., Magee P.J. Vitamin D3 supplementation using an oral spray solution resolves deficiency but has no effect on VO2 max in Gaelic footballers: Results from a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Eur. J. Nutr.* 2017;56:1577–1587. doi: 10.1007/s00394-016-1202-4.